

IMMUNOGENETIC FACTORS ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF ALLERGIC RHINITIS

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The review material includes scientific publications from the past 10 years, published in the international databases E-library, Scopus, and Web of Science

ABSTRACT

One effective approach to studying the role of genetic mechanisms in the development of atopy involves identifying a group of genes, the products of which may be directly or indirectly involved in the development of this pathology, the so-called candidate genes. The greatest difficulty in this regard has proven to be the polygenic nature of AR. Therefore, the traditional "gene-disease" framework for studying AR cannot be used in patients with AR. From a genetic perspective, AR is currently considered a multifactorial polygenic disorder, the hereditary transmission of which is carried out by a group of genes. In the 1980s and 1990s, numerous studies were conducted using molecular genetic methods for the purpose of positional cloning and the study of candidate genes. The main characteristics of the AR phenotype were eosinophilia, atopy, and increased IgE levels [5], resulting from the interaction of multiple gene variants.

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Review results and discussion. One effective approach to studying the role of genetic mechanisms in the development of atopy involves identifying a group of genes, the products of which may be directly or indirectly involved in the development of this pathology, the so-called candidate genes. The greatest difficulty in this regard has proven to be the polygenic nature of AR. Therefore, the traditional "gene-disease" framework for studying AR cannot be used in patients with AR. From a genetic perspective, AR is currently considered a multifactorial polygenic disorder, the hereditary transmission of which is carried out by a

group of genes. In the 1980s and 1990s, numerous studies were conducted using molecular genetic methods for the purpose of positional cloning and the study of candidate genes. The main characteristics of the AR phenotype were eosinophilia, atopy, and increased IgE levels [5], resulting from the interaction of multiple gene variants. At present, many specific AR candidate genes are already known, the function of the protein products of which is associated with the development of this disease: genes of cytokines and their receptors], the interferon gene – γ IFNG, the tumor necrosis factor α gene TNF α , chemokine genes, including the genes of the eotaxin family – RANTES, CCS1, CCL24, CCL26, genes of xenobiotic biotransformation enzymes – GSTM, GSTT, CYP1A1, CYP2C9, CYP2C19, NAT2, the gene of the high-affinity mast cell receptor Fc ϵ RI, etc. According to these researchers, atopic diseases, including allergic rhinitis, should be classified as diseases with an additive polygenic inheritance pattern and a threshold effect, whereby the clinical picture of the disease manifests itself when the combined effects of genetic and environmental factors reach or exceed a threshold value. With a high degree of genetic burden, this threshold is reached under conditions common to most people. On the other hand, prolonged and intense exposure to aggressive external factors can also manifest minimally expressed genetic defects. This approach assumes the presence of a significant number of phenotypically healthy individuals in the population with subthreshold defects that may manifest themselves later.

A key link in the pathogenesis of atopic diseases is the production of proinflammatory cytokines and chemokines in these patients, responsible for the development of chronic allergic inflammation. These are primarily IL-4 and the IL-4 receptor, IL-5, IL-6, IL-10, IL-13, IL-18, TNF- α , TGF- β 1 (transforming growth factor β) [], GM-CSF (granulocyte-macrophage colony-stimulating factor), IFN-gamma (interferon gamma). For a full-fledged allergic reaction, it is necessary to form a large number of chemokines responsible for the chemotaxis of monocytes, basophils (CCL2), induction and attraction (CCL11 or Eotaxin) of eosinophils to the site of the allergic reaction, and the release of the contents of eosinophil granules (CCL5 or RANTES).

Cytokines are classified based on their biochemical characteristics, types of specific cellular receptors, and biological properties. Cytokines include interferons, interleukins, chemokines, a group of tumor necrosis factors, transforming growth factors, and several others. The main common properties of cytokines, which unite them into an independent regulatory system, include: pleiotropism and interchangeability of biological action, mainly the inducible nature of synthesis in response to the penetration of pathogens (antigens) into the body or damage to tissue integrity, the absence of antigen specificity of action, self-regulation of production and the formation of a cytokine network, and signal transmission through interaction with high-affinity cellular receptor complexes. Within the immune system, cytokines mediate the relationship between nonspecific defense reactions and specific immunity, acting in both directions. Chemotoxic cytokines—chemokines—are small signaling proteins that influence the accumulation of inflammatory cells in the mucous membranes in various diseases. CC chemokines—RANTES (regulated on activation, normal T cell expressed and secreted) and the eotaxin family—influence the activity of eosinophils, which are the main factor in tissue damage in allergic diseases. The study of the genes encoding the corresponding chemokines is currently relevant and is actively carried out worldwide in the

molecular genetic study of AR.

Five genes were found to be common to all allergic diseases and IgE: HLA DQB1, HLA DRB1, IL4, IL4RA, and MS4A2. These genes can be called syntropic genes when applied to allergic diseases. In addition, five more genes – HLA DQA1, LTC4S, IL13, IL10, TGFB1 – were common to IgE and all allergic diseases, except one: HLA DQA1 and LTC4S are not associated with food allergy, IL13 – with K/OK, IL10 and TGFB1 – with food allergy. Considering that one of the circumstances complicating this kind of analysis is the insufficient study of genes in relation to a specific pathology, it can be assumed that these five genes are also syntropic for allergic diseases. Thus, the genetic determination of atopic rhinitis is not in doubt. However, data on the main locus responsible for the manifestations of the disease have not yet been obtained. In addition, the genetic background does not explain the rapid increase in atopic diseases observed in recent years. The participation of environmental factors in the development of AR in predisposed individuals is obvious. Summarizing the above data, it can be noted that molecular genetic studies of atopic and other allergic diseases are of great scientific and practical importance. These studies will contribute to an in-depth study of the molecular genetic mechanisms of the pathogenesis of these diseases, the creation of their etiological classification, the development of genetic screening to identify predisposed individuals, and the substantiation of more appropriate approaches to therapy and prevention.

Overall, genetic studies have shown that many functionally interconnected genes are involved in the etiopathogenesis of A3. More than 150 A3 candidate genes have been identified, but only about 40 of them have been associated with A3 in more than five independent studies. Among them are genes encoding cytokines (IL4, IL4RA, IL12B, IL13, TNFA, CCL5), the major histocompatibility complex (HLA-DRB1), 32-adrenergic receptors (ADRB2), xenobiotic biotransformation enzymes (GSTM1, GSTP1, and GSTT1), and genes whose protein products are involved in the recognition of conserved microbial structures (CD 14, TLR2, TLR4, CD 14, CARD 15), in the regulation of epithelial barrier function (FLG, SPINK5), positionally cloned genes (ADAM33, DPP10, GPR154), and the ORMDL3 and GSDMB genes, detected in genome-wide association analysis.

Thus, it can be **concluded** that the study of molecular genetic factors in the development of allergic rhinitis is relevant and requires further research..

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